

ARCSS Program | Message from the ARCSS Committee

ARCSS Note #3 (04 April 2005): ARCSS eTown Meeting Announcement

The ARCSS Committee is sponsoring the second in the series of ARCSS eTown Meetings to discuss with the research community various aspects of ARCSS Program activities. Two online meetings have been scheduled with the same agenda, to give as many researchers as possible an opportunity to discuss and give input on ARCSS Program activities. The April eTown Meetings are scheduled for Friday, 22 April 2005 and Tuesday, 26 April 2005 at 10:00 a.m. Alaska Daylight Time (11:00 a.m. PDT; 12:00 p.m. MDT; 1:00 p.m. CDT; 2:00 p.m. EST)

Advance registration is required. The agenda and other information will be posted on the ARCSS listserv and the ARCSS website at http://www.arcus.org/ARCSS/ETM/April_05/ (http://www.arcus.org/ARCSS/ETM/April_05/)

Forty-seven people participated in the first ARCSS eTown Meeting on Friday, 4 March 2005. The March meeting provided valuable community input on ARCSS planning. Community feedback and recommendations were incorporated by the ARCSS Committee in discussions at the 8-10 March ARCSS Committee meeting in Arlington, VA. The April eTown Meetings will be, in part, the Committee's report back to the community, as well as providing further opportunities for community discussion and recommendations.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION The eTown Meeting platform is HorizonWimba; this platform enables online presentations and real-time interaction. To participate in the web portion of the conference, you will need access to an Internet connection in addition to your phone line; participants also have the option to participate via phone only. Web-platform login and call-in instructions will be sent to all registered participants in advance.

You can prepare in advance by running a wizard (on the computer that you intend to use when you participate) to make sure that your computer is properly configured. To access the wizard, go to <http://channel.horizonwimba.com> (<http://channel.horizonwimba.com>) and click on "run the Setup Wizard." One of the tests run by the set-up wizard prompts the user to check the microphone. Don't worry if you fail this portion of the test. Computer microphones will not be used for the April eTown Meetings, as all the audio will be over traditional teleconference lines.

PLEASE NOTE: Due to upgrades to the HorizonWimba platform, you should run the wizard after the 19 April 2005, even if you have run it successfully in the past.

REGISTRATION

To register for the ARCSS eTown Meeting, go to: http://www.arcus.org/ARCSS/ETM/April_05/ (http://www.arcus.org/ARCSS/ETM/April_05/)

Registration Deadline: Tuesday, 19 April 2005

MORE INFORMATION

For more information about the ARCSS Program coordination, including a list of ARCSS Committee members, go to: <http://www.arcus.org/ARCSS/index.html> (<http://www.arcus.org/ARCSS/index.html>)

For more information about the NSF Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Program, go to: http://www.nsf.gov/funding/pgm_summ.jsp?pims_id=13426&org=ARC (http://www.nsf.gov/funding/pgm_summ.jsp?pims_id=13426&org=ARC)